

EMOTIONAL, SOCIAL, EDUCATIONAL ADJUSTMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to investigate whether there is any significant relationship between adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school students. In this survey study, the investigators used stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample from the population. The stratification was done on the basis of gender and locality of students. The sample consists of 350 higher secondary school students from ten schools in Thanjavur District, TamilNadu, India. The tools used for the present study were Adjustment Inventory developed by A.K.P. Sinha and R.P. Singh (2007) and academic achievement constructed by the investigator. The statistical techniques used for analyzing the data for the present study was Karl Pearson's product moment co-efficient of correlation. The finding shows that, there is a significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustment of higher secondary school students in relation to academic achievement.

Keywords: Emotional Adjustment, Social Adjustment, Educational Adjustment, Academic Achievement, Higher Secondary Students.

INTRODUCTION

The school is the major socialization institution for any child. It is the child's first contact with the world outside the house. For nearly 12 years, a child spends 5 to 7 hours a day in the school. School is one of the most important foundation pillars on which the child's personality develops. Children learn proficiencies in various abilities like learning process and homework, social communications, handling emotion, and the management of day-to-day interactions at home and school (Raju & Rahamtulla, 2007).

In reality, the growing child is dependent on the immediate environment, i.e. the house and the school meet his growth needs. The concern, therefore extends to how the school facilities can be enhanced and improved to meet the growth needs of the children. Every individual from the time he or she steps out of the family and goes to school makes a long series of adjustments between the whole unique personality and the environment. The

ardent desire of each boy and girl to become an individual person having a healthy physique, a growing intellectual ability, a greater degree of emotional poise and increased participation in social groups, such characteristics enhance one's personality (Singh, Tripathi & Mahato, 2014). Even parents, teachers and other significant members of the society to which the person belongs will encourage this desire. According to C.V. Good (1959), Adjustment is the process of finding and adopting modes of behaviour suitable to the environment or the changes in the environment (Mangal, 2002, p.490). It is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs. Thus Adjustment influences the achievement and personality development of the students in school.

Review of Related Studies

Verma and Kumari (2016) studied the academic achievement of children at the elementary stage in

relation to their adjustment. The findings of the study revealed that, a significant relationship exists between adjustment and academic achievement of elementary school students. It was also found that, a significant relationship exists between adjustment and academic achievement of both male and female elementary school students. It was found that, the adjustment of elementary school students is affected by gender.

Nidhi and Kermane (2015) studied the adjustment problems of college students in relation to gender, socio-economic status and academic achievement. The findings of the study showed that, there was no significant difference found in adjustment problems of high academic achievement students and low academic achievement students. There exists a negative relationship between adjustment problems and achievement.

Gill (2014) investigated a study on educational, social and emotional adjustment of boys and girls of visual handicapped students of a special school at Faridabad. The findings show that, there was no significant difference between educational adjustments of the special school students belonging to boys and girls. There was no significant difference between social adjustments of the Special. There was no significant difference between the emotional adjustments of special school students belonging to boys and girls.

Yellaiah (2012) found that, adjustment and academic achievement cause significant difference between male and female student. Government and private school students and rural and urban school students do not cause a difference between adjustment and academic achievement. It is also found that, there is a low positive relationship between adjustment and academic achievement.

Surekha (2008) points out that, a significant positive, high correlation exists between academic achievement and adjustment.

Significance of the Study

Adjustment can be interpreted as both process and the outcome of that process in the form of some attainment

or achievement. When a poor child studies under the street light owing to no electricity at his home, he is said to be in the process of adjustment. What he attains in terms of success in his examination or the fulfillment of his ambition or pride in his achievement is the result of his self and the environment. According to Darwin's theory of evolution, those species which adapted successfully to the demands of living, survived and multiplied while others died out. So, the students who can adapt or adjust to the needs of changing conditions can achieve high, while others lead miserable lives or prove as a menace to the society (Tambawal, 2010). So, the students should change or modify themselves in some way or the other to fit into or accommodate themselves to their environment. But this present generation students lack the tendency of adjustment and they don't know the value or importance of adjustment with themselves and their environment. There is a need for the study of adjustment level of the students under these circumstances. Hence, the researchers have decided to analyse these adjustment levels in this study.

Operational Definition of Key Terms

- ***Adjustment***

Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between the needs and the circumstances. Kulshrestha (1979) explained that, the adjustment process is a way in which the Individual attempts to deal with stress, tensions, conflicts, etc., and meet his or her needs. In this process, the individual also make efforts to maintain harmonious relationship with the environment. L.F. Shaffer (1961) explained that, adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs.

- ***Emotional Adjustment***

It refers to an individual's adaptation in emotional relationships within and with other people, both inside and outside the school, as reflected in the individual's attitudes and behaviour.

- **Social Adjustment**

It refers to an individual's adaptation in social relationships with other people, both inside and outside the school, as reflected in the individual's attitudes and behaviour.

- **Academic Achievement**

Academic Achievement is the performance in school in a standardized series of educational tests. The term is more generally used to describe performance in the subjects of the curriculum. It refers to the marks scored in the Quarterly test that is designed and administered to the sample of students by the investigator himself.

- **Higher Secondary School Students**

Higher Secondary School Students are those students who are studying in standard XI and XII in the higher secondary school students in Thanjavur District, Tamil Nadu, India.

Objectives

- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional, social adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional, social adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school boys.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional, social adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school girls.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional, social adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school rural area students.
- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between emotional, social adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school urban area students.

Null Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher

secondary school students.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school boys.

H₀3: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school girls.

H₀4: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school rural area students.

H₀5: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school urban area students.

Limitations

- This study was limited to 10 higher secondary school students in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu.
- Students from government, government aided and self-financed higher secondary schools were only included in this study.
- The survey method was employed and the questionnaires were used to collect the data.
- The investigators used only the variable adjustment in the dimensions of social, emotional and educational adjustment.

Methodology

The investigators have adopted the survey method of research to study the emotional, social, educational adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school students in Thanjavur district. The investigators used stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample from the population. The stratification was done on the basis of gender and locality of students. The sample consists of 350 higher secondary school students from ten schools in Thanjavur district.

The tools used for the present study were Adjustment Inventory developed by A.K.P Sinha and R.P. Singh (2007)

and academic achievement constructed by the investigator. The statistical techniques used for analyzing the data for the present study were Karl Pearson's product moment co-efficient of correlation.

Data Analysis

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, education adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

From Table 1, it is found that, the calculated values 0.245, 0.216 and 0.316 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 levels of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments of higher secondary school students in relation to the academic achievement.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments, adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school boys.

From Table 2, it is found that, the calculated Karl Pearson product moment coefficient of correlation 'γ' values 0.290, 0.283, 0.243 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between emotional, social,

Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Adjustment Vs Academic Achievement	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks at 5% level
Emotional Adjustment	0.245	Significant
Social Adjustment	0.216	Significant
Educational Adjustment	0.316	Significant
Adjustment	0.351	Significant

(At 5% level of significance for 350 df, the table value of γ is 0.098)

Table 1. Relationship between Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustments and Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students

Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Adjustment Vs Academic Achievement	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks at 5% level
Emotional Adjustment	0.290	Significant
Social Adjustment	0.283	Significant
Educational Adjustment	0.243	Significant
Adjustment	0.362	Significant

(At 5% level of significance for 350 df, the table value of γ is 0.098)

Table 2. Relationship between Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Boys

educational adjustments of higher secondary school boys in relation to academic achievement.

H₀3: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school girls.

From Table 3, it is found that calculated coefficient of correlation 'γ' values 0.276 and 0.237 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between emotional and educational adjustment of higher secondary school girls in relation to academic achievement. The calculated coefficient of correlation 'γ' value 0.093 is lower than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is no significant relationship between social adjustment of higher secondary school girls in relation to academic achievement.

H₀4: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school rural area students.

From Table 4, it is found that, the calculated 'γ' values 0.246, 0.220 and 0.311 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a

Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Adjustment Vs Academic Achievement	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks at 5% level
Emotional Adjustment	0.276	Significant
Social Adjustment	0.093	Significant
Educational Adjustment	0.237	Significant
Adjustment	0.278	Significant

(At 5% level of significance for 350 df, the table value of γ is 0.098)

Table 3. Relationship between Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Girls

Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Adjustment Vs Academic Achievement	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks at 5% level
Emotional Adjustment	0.246	Significant
Social Adjustment	0.220	Significant
Educational Adjustment	0.311	Significant
Adjustment	0.344	Significant

(At 5% level of significance for 350 df, the table value of γ is 0.098)

Table 4. Relationship between Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Rural Area Students

significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments of higher secondary school rural area students in relation to academic achievement.

H₀5: There is no significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school urban area students.

From Table 5, it is found that, the calculated coefficient of correlation 'γ' values 0.309, 0.214 and 0.234 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, there is a significant relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments of higher secondary school urban area students in relation to academic achievement.

Findings

From Table 1, it is found that, the calculated value 0.351 is greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant relationship between adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

From Table 2, it is found that, the calculated 'γ' value 0.362 are greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant relationship between adjustment of higher secondary school boys in relation to academic achievement.

From Table 3, it is found that, the calculated 'γ' value 0.278 is greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant relationship between adjustment of higher secondary school girls in relation to academic

achievement.

From Table 4, it is found that, the calculated coefficient of correlation 'γ' value 0.344 is greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant relationship between adjustment of higher secondary school rural area students in relation to academic achievement.

From Table 5, it is found that, the calculated coefficient of correlation 'γ' value 0.342 is greater than the table value 0.098 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. So, there is a significant relationship between adjustment of higher secondary school urban school students in relation to academic achievement.

Conclusion & Recommendations

From the present study, it is confirmed that, there is a low positive relationship between emotional, social, educational adjustments and adjustment of higher secondary school students in relation to academic achievement. These findings confirm the findings of Mansingbhai & Yasvantbhai (2014), Yellaiah (2012) & Kumar & Dhillon (2010).

The students studying from higher secondary schools are in a need of some psychological support from their parents as well as teachers. So, the parents and teachers must give more guidance and supportive care to the students who are in their school studies. All the higher secondary schools must give importance to providing counseling service to the students who are having emotional and adjustment problems. A well trained counselor should be appointed for giving guidance and counseling services.

The schools must not give importance only to high achievement of their students, but must give importance to teaching to adjust with oneself and with their environment. The schools must often conduct meetings with the parents of the students and make them to know about their child's status. The schools must maintain a separate record for the students' behavior inside the school and must find out the emotionally immature students. This will help them to give counseling. All the government schools must be modified with all the

Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Adjustment Vs Academic Achievement	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks at 5% level
Emotional Adjustment	0.309	Significant
Social Adjustment	0.214	Significant
Educational Adjustment	0.234	Significant
Adjustment	0.342	Significant

(At 5% level of significance for 350 df, the table value of 'g' is 0.098)

Table 5. Relationship between Emotional, Social, Educational Adjustment and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Urban Area Students

facilities like good laboratory, library and well structured classrooms.

Some of the enrichment programmes may be conducted to improve the adjustment of the students with their peer groups and with their family like street play, group assignment, group learning, group dance and other team works. Teachers are the greatest role model for their students. So, at first the teacher must have high level adjustment and emotional stability and must show their students how to adjust with others.

References

- [1]. Good, Carter V. (1959). *Dictionary of Education* (2nd ed.), New York, USA: McGraw Hill Book Co.
- [2]. Kulshrestha, S.P. (1979). *Educational Psychology*. Meerut, India: Loyal Book Depot.
- [3]. Kumar A., & Dhillon J.S., (2010). "Study of academic achievement, values and adjustment of secondary school students in relation to working status of mothers". (Doctoral Dissertation, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar). Retrieved from <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>
- [4]. Mangal S.K., (2002). *Advanced Educational Psychology*. New Delhi: PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
- [5]. Mansingbhai T.S., & Yasvantbhai, H.P. (2014). "Adjustment and academic achievement of higher secondary school student". *Journal of Information, Knowledge and Research in Humanities and Social Sciences*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 128-130. Retrieved from <http://www.ejournal.aessangli.in>
- [6]. Nidhi and Kermene, M. Maqbool, (2015). "Adjustment Problems of College Students in relation to gender, socio-economic status and academic achievement". *International Journal of Current Research*, Vol. 7, No. 4, pp. 14574-14578.
- [7]. Raju M.V.R., & Rahamtulla T.K., (2007). "Adjustment problems among school students". *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 33, No. 1, pp. 73-79.
- [8]. Shaffer, L.F., (1961). *Article in Boring*. Longfield & Welb (Eds.), *Foundation of psychology*. New York, USA: John Wiley.
- [9]. Singh T.K., Tripathi S., & Mahato J., (2014). "Health and Adjustment of High School Students". *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 9-18. Retrieved from <http://oaji.net/articles/2014/1170-1412083822.pdf>
- [10]. Surekha, (2008). "Relationship between students' adjustment and academic achievement". *EduTrack*, Vol. 7, No. 7, pp. 26-31.
- [11]. Tambawal M.U., (2010). "Counselling for enhancement of personal-social and vocational adjustment". *Induction/Orientation for Sokoto State Indigens Undergoing Computer Training Programme of Sokoto State Education Development Trust Fund*. Retrieved from <https://www.academia.edu/3819814>
- [12]. Verma R. Kumar and Kumari S., (2016). "Academic Achievement of Children At Elementary Stage in Relation to Their Adjustment". *Global Journal for Research Analysis*, Vol. 5, No. 1, pp. 310-312.
- [13]. Yellaiah, (2012). "A study of adjustment on academic achievement of high school students". *International Journal of Social Sciences & Interdisciplinary Research*, Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 84-94. Retrieved from <http://www.indianresearchjournals.com>
- [14]. Gill, Satish (2014). "Emotional, Social and Educational Adjustment of Visually Handicapped Students of Special Schools students". *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, Vol. 4, No. 3, pp. 1-4. Retrieved from www.ijsrp.org

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